

matic region with coupling constants of 14 Hz (Table 1) accounts for the (*Z*)-configuration of the styryl moiety. The anilides (1a) used were the authentic (*Z*)-isomers which would cyclise to the corresponding (*Z*)-4-benzylidene-2-methyl-2-imidazol-5-one (2) which in turn would react with the aldehydes to give 3. It should be emphasised that on steric consideration the (*Z*)-compound 2 is more stable than its (*E*)-isomer and there is no question of its undergoing isomerisation during heating. Thus, the configuration of the olefinic centre at 4-position of 3 is (*Z*).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL 90Q spectrophotometer.

1-Aryl-4-benzylidene-2-styryl-2-imidazol-5-ones (3). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2-acetylaminocinnamamide⁷ (1a; 1.0 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (5; 1.1 mol) was heated under reflux in glacial acetic acid (15 ml/g of the anilide) for 2 h, using freshly fused sodium acetate as a catalyst. After the usual work-up the product was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

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Synthesis of New Thiazolidinone Derivatives as Biologically Active Agents

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THIAZOLIDINONES are potential antibacterial¹, antifungal^{2,3} and insecticidal⁴ agents. 1,3,4-Thiadiazole derivatives have been reported to act as antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, insecticidal⁷ and herbici-

dal⁸ agents. Thus keeping the above conjecture in mind, a series of 2-[(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)imino]-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)thiazolid-4-ones (4a-o) and their arylidene derivatives (5a-o) were synthesised.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and visualised by iodine vapour.

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1a-c): The compounds were prepared by the reported method⁹.

Phenyl isothiocyanates (2): The compounds were obtained by reported method¹⁰.

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
4a	OH ₂	H	256	62	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS ₂	51.00 (49.65)	3.50 (3.44)	19.00 (19.31)
4b	OH ₂	CH ₃	258	67	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂	51.50 (51.31)	3.74 (3.94)	18.21 (18.42)
4c	OH ₂	Cl	268	65	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	44.45 (44.23)	2.65 (2.78)	17.20 (17.25)
4d	OH ₂	OCH ₃	282	62	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	48.51 (48.75)	3.85 (3.75)	17.40 (17.50)
4e	OH ₂	Br	210	60	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₄ OS ₂ Br	40.20 (39.02)	2.52 (2.43)	14.80 (15.17)
4f	C ₂ H ₅	H	232	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂	51.52 (51.31)	4.21 (3.94)	18.70 (18.42)
4g	C ₂ H ₅	OH ₂	201	68	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂	52.51 (52.82)	4.51 (4.40)	17.12 (17.61)
4h	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	210	61	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	46.40 (46.08)	3.44 (3.24)	16.00 (16.50)
4i	C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	202	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	50.10 (50.29)	4.41 (4.19)	16.41 (16.76)
4j	C ₂ H ₅	Br	186	59	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Br	41.33 (40.73)	3.81 (2.87)	14.21 (14.62)
4k	C ₂ H ₇	H	198	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂	52.75 (52.82)	4.25 (4.40)	17.40 (17.61)
4l	C ₂ H ₇	OH ₂	234	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS ₂	54.51 (54.21)	4.44 (4.31)	16.50 (16.86)
4m	C ₂ H ₇	Cl	204	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	47.85 (47.65)	3.70 (3.68)	15.45 (15.88)
4n	C ₂ H ₇	OCH ₃	231	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	51.75 (51.72)	4.60 (4.59)	15.75 (16.09)
4o	C ₂ H ₇	Br	162	59	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Br	42.75 (42.31)	3.40 (3.27)	13.85 (14.10)
5a	OH ₂	H	282	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂ O	60.50 (60.31)	3.75 (3.70)	15.00 (14.81)
5b	OH ₂	OH ₂	248	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O	61.50 (61.22)	4.40 (4.08)	14.20 (14.28)
5c	OH ₂	Cl	274	66	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂ OCl	55.30 (55.27)	3.12 (3.15)	13.20 (13.57)
5d	OH ₂	OCH ₃	290	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	54.50 (58.82)	3.60 (3.92)	13.25 (13.72)
5e	OH ₂	Br	292	61	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂ OBr	49.60 (49.89)	2.75 (2.84)	12.00 (12.25)
5f	C ₂ H ₅	H	270	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O	61.40 (61.22)	4.20 (4.08)	14.15 (14.28)
5g	C ₂ H ₅	OH ₂	220	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ S ₂ O	62.21 (62.06)	4.21 (4.43)	13.51 (13.79)
5h	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	280	59	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ S ₂ OCl	56.05 (56.27)	3.41 (3.51)	13.00 (13.13)
5i	C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	218	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.50 (59.71)	4.30 (4.27)	13.25 (13.27)
5j	C ₂ H ₅	Br	191	57	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS ₂ Br	50.52 (50.95)	3.00 (3.18)	11.50 (11.88)
5k	C ₂ H ₇	H	205	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS ₂	62.50 (62.06)	4.00 (4.43)	13.30 (13.79)
5l	C ₂ H ₇	OH ₂	250	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS ₂	62.60 (62.85)	4.40 (4.76)	13.10 (13.33)
5m	C ₂ H ₇	Cl	215	58	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	57.00 (57.20)	3.52 (3.65)	12.50 (12.71)
5n	C ₂ H ₇	OCH ₃	286	56	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	60.20 (60.55)	4.40 (4.58)	12.35 (12.84)
5o	C ₂ H ₇	Br	170	58	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS ₂ Br	51.55 (51.95)	3.25 (3.50)	11.20 (11.54)

N-aryl-(*N'*)-(5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)thiocarbamides (3): Substituted-aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added to ethanolic solution of thiazazole (0.01 mol) under stirring and then heated on a water-bath for 4 h. On cooling the mixture, a white crystalline solid separated out. The solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol, ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=N), 2 850 (SH, CH) and 3 000–3 100 cm^{-1} (NH).

2-(5-Alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-imino-3-(4-substituted-phenylthiazolid-4-ones (4a–o): The thiocarbamide (3; 0.01 mol) and monochloroacetic acid (0.015 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) were heated under reflux for 10 h on a water-bath with occasional shaking. The solvent was then distilled off and poured in cold water, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. All other compounds of the series were synthesised in similar manner (Table 1):

4a (62%), m.p. 256° (Found : C, 51.00 ; H, 3.50 ; N, 19.00. $C_{13}H_{10}N_4S_2O$ requires : C, 49.65 ; H, 3.44 ; N, 19.31%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 730 (C=O), 3 100 (CH_2) and 3 250 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ (TFA) 2.15–2.25 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.5 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–7.6 (5H, m, Ar-H) ; 4g, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 640 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 3 100 (CH_2) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (OH).

5-Arylidine-[3-(4-substituted-phenyl)]-2-[3-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]imino]-thiazolid-4-ones (5a–o) : The compounds were prepared by Knoevenagel condensation of thiazolidinone with aromatic aldehyde using acetate ion as a base. To a solution of benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the thiazolidinone (4 ; 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added anhydrous sodium acetate (0.015 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h with occasional shaking. It was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The solid separated out was filtered, washed successively with water and recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1) : 5l (65%), m.p. 250° (Found : C, 62.60 ; H, 4.40 ; N, 13.10. $C_{22}H_{20}N_4OS_2$ requires : C, 62.85 ; H, 4.76 ; N, 13.33%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 700 (C=O) and 2 950 cm^{-1} (CH) ; 5a, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 610 (C=N), 1 710 (C=O) and 2 900 cm^{-1} (CH) ; δ (TFA) 2.20–2.30 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.2–7.8 (10H, m, ArH).

Antibacterial activity : Compounds 4 and 5 were evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, using the agar-plate diffusion technique¹¹.

From the antibacterial data it was observed that the compounds 4c, 4g, 4h, 4k–m, 5b, 5c, 5g, 5h, 5l and 5n were more toxic to bacteria. A study of the structure-activity relationship showed that there was an increase in the antibacterial property of the compounds with an increase in the alkyl side chain from methyl to propyl. The chlorotoxophore also contributed to increase the activity.

Antifungal activity : Antifungal activity of a few representative compounds was performed against *Aspergillus niger*, *Chetomium globosum* and *Penicillin brevicompactum* using agar-growth technique¹². The compounds in general showed marginal inhibition except compounds 4c, 4d, 4m and 5d which exhibited good inhibition of the growth of fungal colony against all strains used. Introduction of arylidene group at 5-position in thiazolidinone nucleus showed marked fall in the activity.

Antiviral activity : Compounds 4 and 5 were also screened¹³ as antiviral agents against Sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV—a strain of TMV) maintained on host *Cymopsis tetragonoloba* plants. The results revealed that the best compounds of the series were 4c, 4f, 4h, 4k, 4m, 5c, 5f, 5g and 5m (50% inhibition). The variation of alkyl side chain had no note-worthy effect on the activity but the presence of chloro group resulted in a marked increase in the activity.

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Fatty Acids and Sterols from *Melastoma melabathricum*

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MELASTOMA melabathricum Linn.^{1,2} (*Melastomataceae*) an endemic plant of Tripura, Assam and Bangladesh, possesses various medicinal uses³. Previous communications reported the presence of a purple dyestuff, β -sitosterol, melastomic acid, amino acids and aliphatic compounds in different parts of the plant^{3,4}. We now report the isolation and identification of fatty acids and a few more sterols from the aerial parts of the plant.

The aerial parts of *M. melabathricum* were collected from the tilla areas of Agartala in May 1984. Air-dried milled aerial parts (2.0 kg) of the plant was Soxhleted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°), and the crude petrol extract (15.0 g) was chromatographed